

ROSIE

D10.1: Ethics requirements – Informed Consent and Data Protection

Authors: Søren Holm

Editor: Rosemarie Bernabe

Responsible Open Science in Europe

ROSIE

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ABSTRACT:	This deliverable describes the informed consent and anonymisation procedures that are implemented in ROSIE in order to comply with research ethics principles and data protection regulations
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Consortium:

	ROLE	NAME	Short Name	Country
1.	Coordinator	University of Oslo	UiO	Norway
2.	Partner	Austrian Agency for Research Integrity	OeAWI	Austria
3.	Partner	European Citizen Science Association	ECSA	Germany
4.	Partner	European Network of Research Ethics Committees	EUREC	Germany
5.	Partner	Federation of Finnish Learned Societies	TSV	Finland
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1 Introduction

The ROSiE project collects and processes personal research data from interviews and/or focus groups and engagement events with a wide range of stakeholders and stakeholder groups.

These activities do not require research ethics approval in the countries in which the data will be collected or processed. The project will, never the less comply fully with standard research ethics principles and only collect data with the full informed consent of the participating stakeholders (see section 2).

All potential participants are non-vulnerable adults with full capacity to consent.

The processing of the collected data will comply fully with the General Data Protection Regulation (see section 3).

2 Informed consent

Participants in interviews, focus groups and engagement events will be provided with participant information materials prior to their participation, and will be asked to give explicit consent to participation and data collection.

The participant information materials and consent forms will be produced by the Partner responsible for the specific data collection and approved by the Coordinator.

The participant information materials and consent forms will be based on the Partner's local templates and follow the partner's country requirements and institutional SOPs in terms of storage of data. If practicable, the responsible partner institution, with the Coordinating institution **The University of Oslo**, will be specified as joint Data Controllers for specific activities of the project. Otherwise, the responsible partner institution will be the sole Data Controller.

More specifically the participant information materials will contain information about:

- The purpose of the data collection
- Why the potential participant has been contacted
- The activities involved in participation (interview, focus group etc.)
- Data Protection Information, including specification of the types of personal data being collected and processed, the anonymisation procedures, and final deposit in data repository (if relevant)
- Confidentiality
- Right to withdraw
- Funding
- Contact details of Researchers
- Contact details of Coordinator for complaints

3 Data protection and anonymisation

The personal data collected and processed in ROSiE is primarily qualitative research data in the form of audio and video recordings, transcriptions of those recordings, written consultation responses from participants, and field notes. In addition to this the project will collect and process personal data in the form of name, gender and professional role of interview, focus group and engagement event participants.

Audio and video recordings will be transcribed and the transcriptions immediately anonymised, unless participants consented otherwise or when anonymisation is not expected such as in public consultation events. After verification of transcription the audio files will be deleted. Written consultation responses and field notes will also be anonymised. The project will not maintain a link between the anonymised data and the identifying data of the participants.

All data analysis will be performed using the anonymised data, and only anonymised data will be deposited in data repositories at the end of the project (see also Deliverable 9.4 & 9.5 IP/Knowledge and Innovation Management Plan). Research participants will be asked to provide explicit consent to deposition in a data repository as part of the informed consent process prior to data collection.

When the University of Oslo is a Data Controller, it will take charge of registering the activity of the project with NSD - Norsk senter for forskningsdata (from January 2022 Sikt – Kunnskapssektorens tjenesteleverandør sikt.no).

4 REFERENCES

European Commission. "What is a data controller or a data processor?"

https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/law-topic/data-protection/reform/rules-business-and-organisations/obligations/controller-processor/what-data-controller-or-data-processor_en

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